

**WRITING TIPS THAT ENCOURAGE STUDENTS TO WRITE A
PERFECT ESSAY.**

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Annotation: Many IELTS test-takers spend a lot of time training to write great essays. To achieve a desired score, they stuff their essays with uncommon vocabulary, overuse complicated grammar or write too many words. In this article we will discuss some writing tips which we can use while we are writing complex and well-written essays.

Keywords: writing tips, writing style, language, vocabulary, ideas

Writing skills are the skills we use to write effectively. A good writer is someone who can communicate their point to their audience without using unnecessary words so that the other person can understand. Having a range of writing tips can enable students to achieve higher results on exams such as IELTS, TOEFL, CEFR and etc. Writing skills don't just include the physical act of writing. With writing we can express our thoughts without being physically present. As a writer, anyone should have specific skills to use the right words, vocabulary, short phrases, correct tenses, punctuations and more to present clear and understandable content. However, effective writing needs more than this. If students work harder on themselves in order to improve their writing tips, they are likely to achieve desirable scores. But it demands to learn specific and important tips which learners need during the exam. What's more, The following guidances that will help them to be a skilled writer:

First of all, we should choose our writing style. We must not use informal language in academic writing or in essay. Only in general module task 1 it may be asked to write an informal letter. Writing is like building a campfire; one by one, our characters must come out of the woods to help add onto the fire, onto the story.[1]

Secondly, we don't write too many words. It's a bad idea to write more than 300 words in task 2 and more than 200 words in task 1. Firstly, it's difficult for the examiner to read long essays and he/she will check your writing less carefully. Then, we are likely to make more mistakes and have less time to check what we wrote. The most helpful quality a writer can cultivate is self-confidence - arrogance, if we can manage it. We should write to impose ourselves on the world, and we have to believe in our own ability when the world shows no sign of agreeing with us” says Hilary Mantel, famous writer.

Next guidance is not to learn model answers by heart. Anyone should not memorize model answers - they will receive less points for such essay. The chance of getting exactly the same essay as they have learnt is very small. And going off topic will result in achieving a low score. So instead, they have to spend some time learning to adopt advanced vocabulary to make it fit into their answer. This way they will be able to use various words phrases in different writings and show their broad range of vocabulary. In writing the most important thing is to write clearly and coherently. We do not repeat ourselves with different words, avoid being redundant. Also, we have to make sure that each paragraph in Writing task 2 has a central idea. It is very important for IELTS writing that every paragraph in our essay is clearly separated and has its main thought. This simple thing makes your essay neat and coherent.

Besides that, we do not add needless information to our essay and write about what we know. We should write only according to the theme. We do not have to include irrelevant information. If we wander from the subject, we will get a much lower score even for a well-styled answer. In addition, if anyone considers the time, it is better to answer the question that is asked as they have limited time. They are being tested on the quality of their English, not on the quality of their ideas. So they shouldn't worry

about finding the “right answer”. They need a simple idea that they can clearly describe and justify. And make sure their writing is accurate enough. What they write becomes who they are.[2]

The next tip is about to read what they have written. They have to go back and read the paragraph they have just written before they start the next one. They may think that this is a waste of time. If so, they would be wrong. It’s important to link their paragraphs together – what easier way to do that than just read what they have written. Moreover, they do not use bullets in their answers, always write them in full and arrange their basic ideas into different paragraphs. This shows the examiner how well they can organise their points. They do not have to concentrate on writing long and complicated answers. I think, it is a waste of time. Write well, coherent and organise their thoughts well. [3] Besides that, they must not confuse between singular and plural nouns. Always double check their answers for this common mistake. Examiner will check and makes their score lower eventhough there is a little mistake.

Another important thing is to examine the questions properly and see that you cater to all parts of the question and never forget that the completed simply written essay is better than the half-written masterpiece.[4]

In conclusion when we write any formal and informal essays we should know what the meaning of the topic and its aim to be discussed. In this case, we have to read a lot of authentic materials to analyze word choice, grammar structure, comprehension and cohesion.

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